

Local Government in Poland

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Andżelika Mirska

University of Warsaw

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

University of Warsaw: Andželika Mirska
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Adam Nieścioruk/Unsplash

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People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.2. Decisions on Expanding the City Territory at the Expanse of the Rural Area: Consultations with Residents or a Local Referendum?

Andżelika Mirska, *University of Warsaw*

Relevance of the Practice

Communes (*gminas*) are called ‘little homelands’ or ‘schools of democracy’. The Polish Constitution states that the residents of communes may make decisions considering their community in a local referendum.¹⁸² Polish law also provides for an obligation to consult residents.¹⁸³ In addition, various forms of citizens co-decision have proliferated recently, e.g. participatory budgets under the participatory administration model.

The question arises whether the change of the commune (*gmina*) borders belongs to such decisions in which the residents should be authorized to make them. The issue of changing the borders of communes, such as merging, dividing and liquidating communes, has become a very controversial and emotional topic in recent years.

No comprehensive, top-down territorial reform concerning communes, e.g. merging communes to obtain territorially larger units, has been carried out since 1989/1990, since the beginning of the systemic transformation and the restoration of local government in communes. However, the adjustments of communes’ borders are made every year. The incorporation of some areas of rural communes such as individual villages (*sołectwos*)¹⁸⁴ into the neighboring large cities is the specific type of adjustments. Obtaining land for cities development and investments is the aim of such a procedure. It leads to a conflict of interests emerging between rural communes (*rural gminas*) and cities (*urban gminas*).

Rural communes (*rural gminas*) refer to the principle of communes’ identity and territorial stability of communes. The Association of Rural Communes,¹⁸⁵ a national organization representing the rural communes’ interests, has repeatedly expressed its disapproval and an urgent objection to the expansion of urban areas at the expense of rural communes. The

¹⁸² Art 170 of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 1997 and the Act of 15 September 2000 on the local referendum (Dz.U. 2019 poz. 741).

¹⁸³ Art 4(a), 5(a) of the Act of 8 March 1990 on *Gmina* Self-Government, Art 3(a), 3(d) of the Act of 5 June 1998 on *Powiat* Self-Government, Art 10(a) of the Act of 5 June 1998 on Voivodeship Self-Government.

¹⁸⁴ A *sołectwo* (*sołectwo*) is an auxiliary unit of the commune (*gmina*) that does not have the status of local government unit and legal personality. The *sołectwo* are established, transformed and liquidated independently by the commune. The *sołectwo* operate in the area of rural communes and rural-urban communes.

¹⁸⁵ For the website of the Association of Rural Communes, see <<http://www.zgwrp.pl/>>.

Association of Rural Communes indicates the issue of spatial urban sprawl that causes cities to strive for capturing territories surrounded by communes. It is supposed to be a panacea for the problems of urban depopulation.¹⁸⁶

Rural communes support the decision that residents should always decide about border changes and their opinion should be binding as opposed to consultations which are not binding. Rural local governments do not agree to deprive them of a part of their territory for economic reasons in order to increase the area and the urban's wealth.¹⁸⁷

On the other hand, cities indicate the necessity to expand their area and incorporate suburbs to the cities, as suburban residents work and study in the city, use the urban infrastructure and pay taxes to the commune's budget of the place of residence.

Description of the Practice

The decision to change the borders of individual communes in Poland is made by the central government (Council of Ministers). The Act of 8 March 1990 on *Gmina* Self-Government in Article 4 provides that 'establishing and changing the communes (*gminas*) borders are made in a way that ensures the commune's territory as consistent as possible with regard to the settlement and spatial layout, taking into account social, economic and cultural bonds, and ensuring the ability to perform public tasks'.

The act also states that in the process of border changing, it is *necessary* to consult the residents of both municipalities, and a local referendum may also be held. Such a referendum can only be initiated by residents. Importantly, consultations may be conducted in a part of the commune's territory, e.g. in one village (*solectwo*). The referendum is held in the entire commune.

Moreover, the European Charter of Local Self-Government states that 'changes in local authority boundaries shall not be made without prior consultation of the local communities concerned, possibly by means of a referendum where this is permitted by statute'.¹⁸⁸

In the study regarding changes in the communes' borders in Poland, it was calculated that, for instance, in the years 2009-2018 the Polish Government issued a total of 183 decisions to change the borders of local government units, of which 137 concerned the incorporation of

¹⁸⁶ Position of the XVII Congress of Polish Rural Communes of October 20, 2017 on changes to the law regarding the division and changes of the communes borders, <<http://www.zgwrp.pl/attachments/article/1227/ws.%20ochrony%20granic%20gmin.pdf>> accessed 15 March 2021.

¹⁸⁷ Position of the XXXII General Assembly of the Association of Rural Communes of the Polish Republic of June 19, 2018 on changes to the law regarding the division and changes to the borders of communes, <http://www.zgwrp.pl/attachments/article/1354/XXXIIIZO_stanowisko_granice.pdf> accessed 15 March 2021.

¹⁸⁸ Article 5 of the European Charter of Local Self-Government, ratified by Poland in full in 1993.

the commune territory or its parts, most frequently a village (*solectwo*) into the neighboring city.¹⁸⁹

The intensive efforts of the City of Rzeszow to expand its territory are a special case. Rzeszow, a city (urban commune) with county (*powiat*) rights, is the capital and central city of one of the 16 voivodeships. It is located in south-eastern Poland. In 1990, the population of residents was 153,000, in 2005 it was 158,000, and in 2020 it was 197,000. It is currently the 17th largest city concerning population in Poland.

Since 2005, the authorities of the City of Rzeszow have been taking very intensive actions to enlarge the city area. An application is submitted every year to the Council of Ministers (central government) to include neighboring communes or their parts (of villages/*solectwos*). For example, in the 2016 request, there were as many as 12 villages (*solectwos*) that Rzeszow wanted to incorporate. In 2011-2016, the government did not agree to any of Rzeszow's requests. Rzeszow has tried repeatedly to incorporate some villages. Such an example is the Matysowka *solectwo* incorporated into Rzeszow in 2019. Rzeszow unsuccessfully applied for the incorporation of this *solectwo* in 2005, 2007, 2011, and 2017.

Table 5: Stages of the incorporation of some areas of rural communes (*solectwos*/villages) into the City of Rzeszow.

	Name of <i>solectwo</i> /village	Consultation results with residents	Area
2006	Slocina (<i>Słocina</i>) - <i>solectwo</i> in the rural Commune of Krasne	80.4% of the residents of <i>solectwo</i> Slocina <i>against</i> the incorporation into Rzeszow ¹⁹⁰	9.16 km ²
2006	Zależe (<i>Załęże</i>) - <i>solectwo</i> in the rural Commune of Krasne	78% of the residents of <i>solectwo</i> Zależe <i>against</i> the incorporation into Rzeszow ¹⁹¹	5.20 km ²
2007	A part of Przybyszowka (<i>Przybyszówka</i>) - <i>solectwo</i> in the rural Commune of Swilcza (<i>Świlcza</i>)	2004: 81.4% of the residents of <i>solectwo</i> Przybyszowka <i>against</i> the incorporation into Rzeszow ¹⁹²	9.25 km ²

¹⁸⁹ Dagmara Kociuba, 'Zmiany granic administracyjnych miast w Polsce – efekty przestrzenne i społeczno-ekonomiczne [Changes in the Administrative Boundaries of Cities in Poland – Spatial and Socio-Economic Effects]' (2019) 33 *Studia Miejskie* 99 <<https://doi.org/10.25167>>.

¹⁹⁰ Aleksandra Biłska-Bałchank, 'Kształtowanie granic jednostek zasadniczego podziału terytorialnego państwa na przykładzie miasta Rzeszowa [Shaping the Boundaries of Units of the Basic Territorial Division of the Country on the Example of the City of Rzeszów]' (Student scientific conference no 3, University of Warsaw) <<http://m.wspia.eu/dzialalnosc-naukowa/konferencje-naukowe/studenckie-konferencje-naukowe/5460,studencka-konferencja-naukowa-nr-3.html>> accessed 15 March 2021.

¹⁹¹ *ibid.*

¹⁹² Quarterly Journal of Commune of Swilcza, *Trzcionka* (no 32, 2004/2005 winter edition) <https://www.swilcza.com.pl/images/trzcionka/Trzcionka_032.pdf> accessed 15 March 2021; Notice by Head of the Swilcza commune from the 8 November 2004 on the official results of consultations on the change of the boundaries of the Swilcza Commune, conducted on 7 November 2004 <http://www.swilcza.i-gmina.pl/files/3255_Obwieszczenia_-_konsultacje.pdf> accessed 15 March 2021.

		2005: 75.92% of the residents of <i>sołectwo</i> Przybyszowka <i>against</i> the incorporation into Rzeszów ¹⁹³	
2008	The remaining part of Przybyszowka - <i>sołectwo</i> in the rural Commune of Swilcza	Approx. 80% of the residents of Przybyszowka <i>in favor</i> of the incorporation into Rzeszów ¹⁹⁴	7 km ²
		No data available on the website of Swilcza commune	
2008	Zwieczyca (<i>Zwiężczyca</i>) - <i>sołectwo</i> in the urban-rural Commune of Boguchwała (<i>Boguchwała</i>)	2004: 91.49% of the residents of the entire commune <i>against</i> the incorporation into Rzeszów ¹⁹⁵	7.2 km ²
2009	A part of the village Biała (<i>Biała</i>) from the urban-rural Commune of Tyczyn	59.8% of the residents of the entire commune <i>against</i> the incorporation into Rzeszów	6.1 km ²
		61% of the residents of Biała <i>in favor</i> of the incorporation into Rzeszów ¹⁹⁶	
2010	A part of Miłocin (<i>Miłocin</i>) from the urban-rural Commune of Glogow Malopolski (<i>Głogów Małopolski</i>)	No data	1.24 km ²
2010	Budziwoj (<i>Budziwój</i>) from the urban-rural Commune of Tyczyn)	55% of the residents of the entire commune <i>against</i> the incorporation into Rzeszów.	17.5 km ²
		58% of the residents of the village of Budziwoj <i>in favor</i> of the incorporation into Rzeszów ¹⁹⁷	
2017	Bzianka (<i>sołectwo</i> in the rural Commune of Swilcza)	65.29% of the <i>sołectwo</i> of Bzianka <i>in favor</i> of the incorporation into Rzeszów.	4.04 km ²

¹⁹³ Notice by Head of the Swilcza commune of 2 February 2005 on the official results of consultations on the change of the boundaries of the Swilcza Commune held from 20 to 31 January 2005 <www.swilcza.i-gmina.pl/files/3602_Obwieszczenia_-_konsultacje2.pdf> accessed 15 March 2021.

¹⁹⁴ 'Zmiana granica – zmiana zdania?' (*Super Nowości*, 18 May 2017) <<http://supernowosci24.pl/zmiana-granica-zmiana-zdania/>> accessed 15 March 2021.

¹⁹⁵ Protocol no XXIII/2004 of the Boguchwała Commune Council held on November 4, 2004 <<https://www.bip.boguchwala.pl/183,24706,187/187/art1543.html>> accessed 15 March 2021.

¹⁹⁶ 'Biała i Budziwój chcą do Rzeszowa' (*nowiny 24*, 31 January 2008) <<https://nowiny24.pl/tyczyn-biala-i-budziwoj-chca-do-rzeszowa/ar/5997873>> accessed 15 March 2021.

¹⁹⁷ <<https://bip.tyczyn.pl/?c=mdTresc-cmPokazTresc-11-420>> accessed 15 March 2021.

		(498 people were entitled to vote. 244 people participated in the consultation) ¹⁹⁸	
2019	Matysowka (<i>Matysówka</i>), a part of the urban-rural Commune of Tyczyn	52.57% of the residents of the entire commune <i>against</i> the incorporation into Rzeszow.	5.3 km ²
		63% of the residents of Matysowka <i>in favor</i> of the incorporation into Rzeszow ¹⁹⁹	
2019	The second part of Milocin - from the urban-rural Commune of Glogow Malopolski	68.62% of the residents of the entire commune <i>against</i> the incorporation into Rzeszow The residents of the <i>solectwo</i> of Milocin: voting at a village meeting, 62 out of 80 voting were in favor of the incorporation into Rzeszow ²⁰⁰	0.9 km ²
2021	Podgwizdow Nowy (<i>Pogwizdów Nowy</i>) - Glogow Malopolski	2018: 68.62% of the residents of the entire commune <i>against</i> the incorporation into Rzeszow ²⁰¹ . 2019: 92.84% of the entire commune <i>against</i> the incorporation into Rzeszow. 82.2% of the residents of the <i>solectwo in favor</i> of the incorporation (402 people) ²⁰²	2.4 km ²

The incorporation of the neighboring areas in 2005–2021 resulted in an increase in the Rzeszów city's area by 75.27 km² (from 53.7 km² to 128.97 km²) and the population by 35,000 (from 158,000 to 197,000).

¹⁹⁸ 'Results of the Consultations in the Commune of Tyczyn of 1 February 2009' (*Urząd Miejski w Tyczynie*, 4 February 2009) <<https://rzeszow.wyborcza.pl/rzeszow/1,34962,19861425,powiekszenie-rzeszowa-niedziela-w-bziancie-z-tadeuszem-ferencem.html>> accessed 15 March 2021.

¹⁹⁹ Justification to the Regulation of the Council of Ministers of 25 July 2018 on establishing the borders of some communes and cities and granting the city status to some localities. Opinion of the Podkarpackie Voivode of 27/04/2018 regarding the application for a change in the territorial division regarding the incorporation of some communes to Rzeszów City: Tyczyn, Boguchwała, Głogów Małopolski and Trzebownisko <<https://bip.rzeszow.uw.gov.pl/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/solectwa.pdf>> accessed 20 March 2021.

²⁰⁰ *ibid.*

²⁰¹ *ibid.*

²⁰² Ordinance of the Council of Ministers of 31 July 2020 RM-110-109-20 in the case of establishing the borders of some municipalities of cities, granting some localities the status of a city, changing the name of the municipality and the seat of the municipal authorities <<http://urbnews.pl/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/dokument457287.pdf>> accessed 20 March 2021.

Rzeszów is still leading up to strengthen its position as a metropolitan center in south-eastern Poland. The goal is intended to be achieved by successive incorporation of other communes neighboring with Rzeszów and increasing its territory and population.

Figure 19: Territorial development of the City of Rzeszów²⁰³

The City of Rzeszów is planning further requests for the incorporation of further villages (*solectwos*): a part of the area of the *solectwo* of Raclawowka (*Raclawówka*) from the Boguchwala (*Boguchwała*) commune, the area of the *solectwo* of Zaczernie and Nowa Wies (*Nowa Wieś*) and a part of the area of the *solectwo* of Jasionka from the Trzebownisko commune and the incorporation with the entire Commune of Swilcza (*Świlcza*). In the consultations, the residents of all these areas were against incorporating them into the city.²⁰⁴ There is an international airport (14 km from the center of Rzeszow) and the Podkarpackie Science and Technology Park Aeropolis in the area of the *solectwo* of Jasionka. In consultations

²⁰³ 'How our City Grew' (*City of Rzeszow*, undated) <<https://www.erzeszow.pl/692-rozszerzenie-granic-rzeszowa/13520-jak-roslo-nasze-miasto.html>> accessed 16 March 2021.

²⁰⁴ 'Zmiana granica – zmiana zdania?' (*Super Nowości*, 18 May 2017) <<http://supernowosci24.pl/zmiana-granica-zmiana-zdania/>> accessed 15 March 2021.

in 2015, 96.41 per cent of the residents of Jesionka were against the incorporation into Rzeszow.

After analyzing the data on the incorporation into Rzeszow of some villages (*solectwos*) in 2005-2021, it can be noticed that:

- in most cases, residents of rural communes were against losing a part of the territory to the City of Rzeszow;
- consultations are non-binding and according to the examples, the borders of rural communes have often changed against the will of the residents.

However, there is a question considering whether the decision should be made by the residents of the entire rural commune or only the residents of a particular area (of a *solectwo*/village). For example, consultations conducted in the Tyczyn commune in 2016 showed the problem. Tyczyn commune is an urban-rural commune, consisting of the town of Tyczyn and four *solectwos*. The consultations were conducted in the entire commune: in total 57.3 per cent of the residents were against the fact that one *solectwo* (Matysowka) should be taken from the Tyczyn commune and incorporated into Rzeszow. However, in the area of this *solectwo*, 66.6 per cent of the residents were in favor of being incorporated into Rzeszow.²⁰⁵

A similar situation was in the Glogow Malopolski commune in 2019. The consultations concerned the loss of the village of Pogwizdow Nowy (*Pogwizdów Nowy*) to Rzeszow. 93 per cent of the residents of the entire commune were against the separation of this village from the commune. Nevertheless, the residents of this village conducted their separate consultations and claimed that 489 residents took part in them which amount to 39 per cent of the village residents. 402 people, representing 82.2 per cent of voters, supported the incorporation of the village into Rzeszow²⁰⁶.

Provided that consultations are non-binding and may be conducted in a part of the commune area, e.g. in one village (*solectwo*), a local referendum may be conducted only in the area of the entire commune.

The case of the Krasne commune:

- first, there were consultations;
- then, a local referendum was held in 2016 in the entire commune. High attendance: 56 per cent.²⁰⁷

²⁰⁵ 'Wyniki konsultacji przyłączenia Matysówki do Rzeszowa' (*Gmina Matysówka*, 22 February 2016) <<http://www.matysowka.pl/ogloszenia/wyniki-konsultacji>> accessed 15 March 2021.

²⁰⁶ <<https://bip.rzeszow.uw.gov.pl/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/opinia.pdf>> accessed 15 March 2021.

²⁰⁷ Protocol of establishing the result of the local referendum on the voluntary merger of the Krasne commune with the City of Rzeszów and the incorporation of the Malawa commune into Rzeszów of 23 October 2016. <<https://www.gminakrasne.pl/biuletyn-informacji-publicznej/wybory/referendum-gminne-2016/>> accessed 16 March 2021.

The first question concerned the incorporation of the entire Krasne commune into Rzeszów: approximately 62 per cent of the commune's residents were against the incorporation. The second question was about the incorporation of one part of the Krasne commune (Malawa *solectwo*). However, the residents of the entire commune voted. 1,771 people voted for the incorporation of Malawa into Rzeszów, and 2,810 people against it.²⁰⁸ Malawa was the only *solectwo* where the majority of residents voted to incorporate into Rzeszów. 515 people were in favor of incorporating into Rzeszów, and 494 people against it.²⁰⁹

Considering consultations with the residents of the City of Rzeszów, they are held very often and therefore little interest is aroused: about 1.36 per cent – 5 per cent of the residents participate in the vote. Nevertheless, about 90 per cent of voters support the expansion of the city borders.²¹⁰ Moreover, there are also critical voices claiming that the city is investing mainly in newly acquired areas, building a school, and not in the city center.²¹¹

Assessment of the Practice

Changing the borders of communes is associated with many problems. Rzeszów is not the only example. Other cities are also making efforts to increase their territory at the expense of neighboring communes. In terms of the compulsory consultation with residents, the following problem areas should be identified:

- how to solve the issue of consultations with residents, how and where to conduct them diligently;
- whether a referendum should be obligatory instead of non-binding consultations. Currently, the referendum is not obligatory. Nevertheless, at the residents request, it may be mandatory. The referendum is conducted according to the general procedure under the Act of 15 September 2000 on the local referendum;
- the problem of financing consultations and referendums. Residents do not want to submit a request for a referendum because they have to participate in the costs of holding a referendum;

²⁰⁸ The inhabitants of the Krasne commune do not want to go to Rzeszów. Full results of the referendum on the 'Rzeszów News - Information portal', <<https://rzeszow-news.pl/mieszkanicy-gminy-krasne-nie-chca-do-rzeszowa-wyniki-referendum/>> accessed 16 March 2021.

²⁰⁹ Joanna Pasterczyk, 'Gmina Krasne przeciwko połączeniu Malawy z Rzeszowem. Radni zagłosowali na nadzwyczajnej sesji, mieszkańcy są oburzeni' (*Wyborcza.pl*, 8 February 2019) <<https://rzeszow.wyborcza.pl/rzeszow/7,34962,24440970,gmina-krasne-przeciwko-polaczeniu-malawy-z-rzeszowem-radni.html>> accessed 16 March 2021.

²¹⁰ 'Public Consultations on the Change of the Borders of the City of Rzeszów' (*Bulletin of Public Information of Rzeszów*, undated) <<https://bip.erzeszow.pl/107-wyszukiwarka/2182-wyniki-wyszukiwania.html?srch-term=wyniki+konsultacji&srch-muid=w+ca%C5%82ym+serwisie>> accessed 16 March 2021.

²¹¹ For further information, see <<https://bip.rzeszow.uw.gov.pl/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/solectwa.pdf>> accessed 16 March 2021.

- changing borders is a way to enlarge cities that want to build their central position in the region. This is how cities can build their positions as metropolis in the region. This is a problem of managing metropolitan regions. There is a question considering the necessity of another top-down way to build metropolitan territorial units.²¹² However, the most common model in Poland is based on voluntary cooperation between local government units in the functional areas of cities (including metropolitan areas);
- rural communes and urban-rural communes complain that they are losing attractive areas, as well as budget revenues. Residents of rural communes are afraid of higher taxes in the city;
- whether the inhabitants of rural communes should be asked for their opinion at all, because it inhibits the development of cities.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

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²¹² See report section 4 on local government structure and the example of establishing the Upper Silesian and Zagłębie Metropolis [Górnośląsko-Zagłębiowska Metropolia] as the first territorial unit of a metropolitan quality in Poland, report section 4.3.

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

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